

Funded by
the European Union

EU-CIEMBLY

Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

Deliverable 3.4

Report on the EU-CIEMBLY Pilots' Design

v1

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project number	101132694
Project acronym	EU-CIEMBLy
Project name	EU-CIEMBLy: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly
Project website	https://www.eu-ciembly.eu/en/home

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Title	Report on the EU-CIEMBLy Pilots' Design
Deliverable	Deliverable 3.4
Work Package	WP3
Leader	UE
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Authors' acknowledgements	The authors would like to thank Lara Greaves (VUW) and Ileana Steccolini (UE) for providing feedback, as well as Lucía Muñoz Benito (UC) for providing administrative support.
Reviewers	Eric Jensen (IMI), Rituparna Roy (UW), Dulce Lopes (UC)
Type	R - Report
Due date	30/11/2025
Submission date	28/11/2025
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
License	CCBY

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Comments
v0.1	10.11.2025	UE, UniBG, IMI	First version
v0.2	17.11.2025	UE	Addressing reviewers' comments
v1	28.11.2025	UE, UniBG, IMI	Final version after post-review check and submission to the EC

Karatzia A., O'Connor, N., Woodward, S., Noles S., Barbera, C., Di Maso A., Mariani, L., Sicilia M., (2025) *Report on the EU-CIEMBL Y Pilots' Design*, EU-CIEMBL Y Deliverable 3.4 <https://www.eu-ciembly.eu/en/home>

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CSO	Civil Society Organisation
PMIMG	People belonging to multiple intersecting marginalised groups
FRA	Fundamental Rights Agency

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement number 101132694. Deliverable 3.4 reflects only the author's view. The Commission is not responsible for its content or any use that may be made of the information it contains.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 3.4 marks the project's transition from evaluating existing citizens' assembly practices to designing three pilots that aim to test how intersectionality can be operationalised in practice. Building on the project's analytical and normative dimension (comprised of the qualities of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation), and the categorising dimension (made up of input, throughput, and output choices), the pilots which will take place in Work Package 4 aim to translate theory into practice by selecting concrete design features to examine across local, national, and transnational levels.

The EU-CIEMBLY pilot citizens' assemblies are a means to test whether selected design features, chosen from the project's operationalisation models set out in Deliverable 2.3, can be translated into practice to enhance intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation. In other words, the three pilots are where the project's three categories of design choices at the input, throughput, and output stages will be examined across three governance levels: local, national, and transnational.

The present deliverable aims to explain both the objectives of the pilots in more detail, and the methodology developed to design the three pilots through an intersectional lens. We explain that, in terms of methodology, four key considerations guide the design of the pilots: (1) the need to be explicit about our normative understanding of intersectionality; (2) the need to be mindful of our own positionality; (3) the need to adopt a context-based approach; and (4) the need to choose (and subsequently design around) targeted interventions that can improve current practices. We then explain the general parameters that apply to all three pilots before detailing the targeted interventions that we have chosen for each of the pilots, as well as the cross-cutting intervention of embedding intersectionality in the facilitation stage of the assemblies. The macro design plans found here in Deliverable 3.4 will be followed in Deliverable 4.1 with the micro design plans for each pilot, and in Deliverable 4.2 with details of the guidance to be provided to the facilitators of each pilot.

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I. Introduction

1. The Purpose of the Deliverable: From Evaluating to Designing

The present report signals the transition of the EU-CIEMBLY project from the stage of **'evaluating'** current citizens' assembly practices to that of **designing** the three pilots that are to be tested by the project team in Work Package 4 at a local, national, and transnational level. As explained in Deliverable 2.2, intersectionality is used in our project as an analytical framework with two broad purposes, namely:

- (1) to diagnose and assess gaps in the consideration of intersectionality within the context of citizens' assemblies i.e. to 'problematise' the issue; and,
- (2) to propose innovative solutions to those same gaps by developing recommendations, in Work Package 5, for an intersectionality-oriented (EU) citizens' assembly.

While Deliverable 2.2 and Deliverable 3.3 undertook the first, 'diagnostic' task by evaluating citizens' assembly practice in the existing literature and in light of our analytical framework respectively, Deliverable 3.4 sets out our **overarching ideas and plans** for the three pilots that are to be tested by the project team in Work Package 4. In other words, this deliverable focuses on the second function of intersectionality as an analytical lens, namely the use of intersectionality to 'address' the gaps already problematised and to test potential solutions. As a reminder of its four dimensions, an 'abridged' version of the EU-CIEMBLY framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly is set out in Figure 1:

EU-CIEMBLY Framework for an Intersectionality-Oriented Citizens' Assembly		Intersectionality
1. Analytical and normative dimension	Intersectionality as an analytical lens informs the qualities of:	
	Equality Inclusion Good deliberation	
2. Categorising dimension	Which are then used to inform citizens' assembly design choices , categorised according to:	
	Input choices Throughput choices Output choices	
3. Operationalising dimension	Which are incorporated through one or more of the models for operationalising intersectionality in citizens' assemblies	
4. Evaluation and recommendations dimension	Which then inform the development of:	
	An Intersectionality-Oriented Citizens' Assembly	

Figure 1. The EU-CIEMBLY framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly (abridged version)

Our initial literature review (Deliverable 2.1) and theoretical analysis (Deliverable 2.2) established the normative framework for this project. Subsequently, our empirical explorations in Deliverable 3.3 *confirmed our central hypothesis* that existing citizens' assembly practices and their evaluations are not adequately designed to capture or address intersectional marginalisation. Rather, what we have seen is that the idea of intersectionality is indirectly considered through efforts at diversity. These efforts, which encapsulate general conceptions of equality, inclusion,

and good deliberation do not (necessarily) match the intersectional conceptions of equality, inclusion, and good deliberation, which are the qualities underpinning the normative and analytical dimension of our project. Moreover, the secondary analysis of available datasets undertaken in Deliverable 3.3 revealed significant limitations, such as a lack of linked demographic data and inconsistent evaluation metrics, which reinforces the need for new, dedicated intersectionality-informed models and evaluation frameworks. For this reason, the pilot designs presented in this deliverable are informed by: (1) the qualitative interviews with practitioners conducted for Deliverable 3.3; and (2) aspects of the theoretical models developed in Deliverable 2.3 in such a way as to address the empirical gap identified in Deliverable 3.3 by explicitly designing and evaluating our pilot assemblies through the lens of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation.

The design and planning for the EU-CIEMBLY pilots is divided across three deliverables. As has been recognised as good practice elsewhere, we have separated the planning work into macro- and micro-design phases (White et al., 2022; Ayles, 2025). In the EU-CIEMBLY macro-design phase, as detailed in Deliverable 3.4, strategic decisions are undertaken regarding the selection and application of components of the theoretical model(s) developed in Deliverable 2.3. These decisions determine how the models will be operationalised across the different levels of the pilot citizens' assemblies — local, national, and transnational. It is explained that our method for the incorporation of intersectionality considerations into the design of the pilots is guided by four key considerations, namely: (1) the need to be explicit about our normative understanding of intersectionality; (2) the need to be mindful of our own positionality; (3) the need to adopt a context-based approach; and (4) the need to choose (and subsequently design around) targeted interventions that can improve current practices. As explained below, we have designed targeted interventions that are specific to each pilot and are inspired by the theoretical models found in Deliverable 2.3. We have also designed a cross-cutting intervention which concerns the way in which facilitation will take place across all three pilots, given its particular importance to intersectionality considerations. The particular details of *how* we will design the facilitation across the three pilots is then elaborated on further in Deliverable 4.2.

Having set out the macro-design processes in the present deliverable, the team will move into a more detailed preparation phase along the input-throughput-output stages, that includes several more specific decisions, actions, and activities (i.e., the micro-design phase). These include further engagement with other stakeholders, such as NGOs and CSOs, specific recruitment

actions, communication activities, booking the venues for the face-to-face pilots, deciding the software to be used for the online pilots, and reaching out to specific experts and witnesses. We anticipate that many of these activities might overlap or happen simultaneously, and that some of our earlier design choices may have to be modified in light of subsequent developments. A certain degree of **flexibility**, therefore, has guided the design—and will guide the implementation of—our pilots. Indeed, our engagement with intersectionality theory in Deliverable 2.2, has shown the importance of context-specific analysis, reminding us of the need to remain flexible and accommodating of local considerations and how power relations operate in a given context.

The forthcoming Deliverable 4.1 will set out the ‘micro-design’ choices made by our team. Subsequently, Deliverable 4.2 will focus on a specific part of the design process, which connects the design stage and the implementation stage, namely the training programme for the pilots’ facilitators. As will be explained later, an intersectional approach to the planning and implementation of the facilitation stage of citizens’ assemblies, and other deliberative mini-publics more broadly speaking, is a key avenue through which to embed intersectional inclusion, equality, and good deliberation considerations in practice.

Figure 2. The planning outputs for the EU-CIEMBLY pilots’ design

2. Structure of the Deliverable

The report proceeds as follows. Section II sets out the **objectives of the pilots** as a whole. It explains the connection between the pilots and the project’s framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens’ assembly (Figure 3). Section III sets out the intersectionality-informed methodology that will be applied across the three pilots. This methodology consists of a way of integrating **key intersectionality considerations** into the design of the assemblies to enable the application of intersectionality in practice. Section IV explains the **interventions** that each pilot

aims to contribute to the project's overall recommendations while also setting out the macro design choices that will support these interventions. Section V explains the **cross-cutting intervention** of embedding intersectionality considerations in the facilitation stage. Section VI concludes.

II. The Objectives of the EU-CIEMBLY Pilots

Previous work conducted under the EU-CIEMBLY project set out the project's finalised framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly design, which combines the analytical and normative as well as the categorising dimensions (developed under Deliverable 2.2) with the operationalising dimension (developed under Deliverable 2.3). These three dimensions, in addition to feedback that we received during a two-day workshop organised in July 2025 (Deliverable 3.2) and the work that has taken place under Work Package 3¹ have been informing the design of the pilots. In turn, the fourth dimension looks to evaluate the eventual citizens' assembly pilots and to make recommendations for the project as a whole. **In this framework, which is depicted in full in Figure 3 below, the pilots are a means through which we wish to test specific design features and draw some conclusions as to their potential to successfully operationalise intersectionality in citizens' assembly design.**

While Deliverable 2.3 offered a series of potential choices and trade-offs for operationalising intersectionality in citizens' assemblies, its purpose was not to suggest a single, practical, and implementable framework for a specific pilot. Instead, it proposed a variety of theoretical models of how intersectionality *could* be embedded in the design features and practices of a citizens' assembly (Deliverable 2.3, p. 11). In this sense, Deliverable 2.3 provided a broad theoretical menu of possibilities—and combinations of possibilities—for implementing intersectionality in citizens' assemblies (Deliverable 2.3, p. 7). Deliverable 3.4 builds on the work of Deliverable 2.3 by considering ways in which *the pilots* can operationalise these possibilities and permutations.

In addition to explaining which of the six models of Deliverable 2.3 have inspired the design of the pilots, Deliverable 3.4 also explains why those models were chosen across the various levels of our analysis (local, national, and transnational). In doing so, the present deliverable also considers the findings of Deliverable 3.3, which offered an empirical angle to the link between citizens' assembly design and intersectionality. A project of this scope and nature also requires decisions to be made as to which features to test within the practical limitations that frame the project, but which also allows the project team to focus on those interventions that we believe have the most potential to further the intersectional design and delivery of citizens' assemblies in accordance with the project's overarching framework. Therefore, the three pilots are not meant to be a direct

¹ See Deliverable 3.1 for a summary of the data collection that was undertaken in Work Package 3, and Deliverable 3.3 that uses the findings of that work in evaluating current citizens' assembly practices.

translation of specific models from Deliverable 2.3 but rather a pragmatic attempt to operationalise aspects of those models in practice.

EU-CIEMBLY Framework for an Intersectionality-Oriented Citizens' Assembly			
1. Analytical and normative dimension	Intersectionality as an analytical lens informs the qualities of:		
	Equality	Inclusion	Good deliberation
2. Categorising dimension	Which are then used to inform citizens' assembly design choices , categorised according to:		
	Input choices: Governance, organisation and management; selection and recruitment of participants; topic and agenda-setting	Throughput choices: Experts and witnesses in the educative phase; facilitation; deliberation	Output choices: Influence on public decision-making processes; impact on participants
3. Operationalising dimension	Which are incorporated through one or more of the models for operationalising intersectionality in citizens' assemblies:		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Model 1: Descriptive Representation; ● Model 2: Discursive Representation; ● Model 3: Subaltern Counterpublics; ● Model 4: Power Sharing; ● Model 5: Agonistic Pluralism; ● Model 6: Relationality and Interdependence. 		
4. Evaluation and recommendations dimension	Which then inform the development of:		
	An Intersectionality-Oriented Citizens' Assembly		

Intersectionality

Figure 3. The EU-CIEMBLY framework for an intersectionality-oriented citizens' assembly

For research purposes, the pilots are, therefore, not only a valuable contribution in and of themselves, but also the means to an end, i.e., to examine and evaluate intersectionality interventions in the context of citizens' assemblies and potentially in democratic innovations more broadly speaking. We aim to study, through the pilots, whether embedding **specific design choices** in the input, throughput, and/or output stage of the citizens' assemblies design and implementation, can enhance the **qualities** of intersectional inclusion, equality, and good deliberation in such assemblies.

In their piece on using experiments to study democratic innovations, Grönlund and Herne (2019) explain that 'experimental research is usually motivated by willingness to test theories. Based on the theory, specific hypotheses are formulated and these are then tested with an experimental design. Theories are then challenged or given support depending on the results of the experiment'. However, they explain that theories relating to democratic innovations—i.e., theories on deliberative and participatory democracy—are normative characterisations of ideal states of affairs rather than descriptive theories describing the state of affairs. This makes the relationship between theory and empirical research 'atypical'. Having said that, while normative theories cannot be tested as such, experiments on democratic innovations seek to test the empirical claims contained in the theories. (Grönlund & Herne, 2019; Setälä & Herne, 2014).

In the field of democratic innovation, the notion of experimentation typically entails investigating the potential of practices that lie outside, or provide alternatives to, current institutionalised democratic forms/systems. Experimenting with democratic mini-publics usually takes place because the researcher is interested in identifying the influence of different types of organisational arrangements on participants' opinions and attitudes. The researcher may also be interested to study whether democratic innovations have the type of positive consequences that they claim to have: whether e.g., the participants' opinions change and depolarise, whether trust and political efficacy increase, and whether mutual understanding is achieved (Grönlund & Herne, 2019). Experimenting with democratic mini-publics can also help detect **best practices in organising democratic innovations** especially regarding specific features of those innovations such as the way of voting in reaching a group level verdict (Grönlund & Herne, 2019). In other words, experimenting with democratic mini-publics can help identify how design features work in practice against their goals.

Connected to the above, the motivation behind the EU-CIEMBLY pilots is linked back to the EU-CIEMBLY project's overall objective, which is to make recommendations for embedding intersectional considerations into (EU) citizens' assemblies.

In this sense, the pilots aim to provide empirical evidence on the effectiveness of attempts to embed intersectionality considerations in the design, implementation, and evaluation of citizens' assemblies as forums seeking to enhance citizens' public participation.

Our theoretical work so far on the project assumes that an intersectional analytical lens can and should be a consideration in citizens' assemblies. Where previous work on citizens' assemblies, as discussed in Deliverable 2.2, has primarily focused on inclusion and diversity, applying an intersectional analytical lens enables a deeper understanding of how overlapping systems of structural oppression impact the participation and exclusion of persons belonging to multiple intersecting marginalised groups (PMIMG) in such participatory fora. Embedding intersectionality through the design choices of a citizens' assembly attempts to challenge and account for intersecting power dynamics, addressing structural barriers and norms, and promoting participation and good deliberation. **The current stage of the project moves to testing the ways in which such a lens can inform citizens' assemblies practices.** This will be done via **targeted intersectional interventions** that we have designed based on the research conducted so far across all project deliverables. As will be further explained below, one of these interventions is cross-cutting (e.g., it concerns facilitation across all pilots) while the others are tailored to the specific context of each pilot. Overall, we chose these interventions as the ones we believe are particularly amenable to intersectional considerations within the scope and the inevitable limitations of our project. These interventions constitute one element of our proposed **methodology** for incorporating intersectionality into the design and delivery of the pilot citizens' assemblies at the local, national, and transnational levels.

III. Methodology for Incorporating Intersectionality into the Pilot Citizens' Assemblies

In Deliverable 2.2, we explained how Crenshaw's articulation of intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989) has inspired an extensive literature theorising and engaging with that concept. The difficulties associated with turning intersectionality from theory into practice across various fields is also well documented in the literature, particularly the need to translate theoretical conceptions of intersectionality in a user-friendly way (Hankivsky et al., 2014). As Hankivsky et al. (2014, p. 2) note, '[t]aking on an intersectionality study/analysis can be incredibly intimidating', not least due to the fact that 'although intersectionality theory provides a conceptually solid framework with which to examine the social locations of individuals and groups within the broader interlocking structures of power relations, the methodological choices available to do so and/or guidance offered on *how* to do so are severely limited'. Others have noted that there are many different 'applied' conceptions of intersectionality, some of which actually serve to hinder rather than to further intersectionality understood as the product of intersecting power relations, structures, and dynamics i.e., the theoretical conception of intersectionality employed by this project (Christoffersen, 2021).

Key methodological challenges have also been highlighted in the context of doing intersectional analysis—something that is part and parcel of our pilot stage insofar as we will seek to evaluate our interventions to draw findings and policy recommendations. Christensen and Jensen (2012), for instance, note that 'while overall principles and abstract methodology have already been extensively discussed, there has been less debate about concrete intersectional methodology and analysis (p. 110)'. A systematic review from 2021 further shows that the uptake of intersectionality in quantitative studies is relatively recent in comparison to its use in qualitative studies (Bauer et al., 2021). In their review, Bauer et al. (2021) show that intersectionality is frequently misunderstood when bridging theory into quantitative methodology and point to the need for further work to: ensure that researchers understand key features defining quantitative intersectionality analyses; improve reporting practices for intersectional analyses; and, develop and adapt quantitative methods vis-a-vis intersectionality.

Attempts to guide the transposition of intersectionality from theory to practice have more recently started taking place across various fields in the form of Guides, Resources, and Toolkits. Some examples include 'The Intersectionality Policymaking Toolkit' (Hull et al., 2024) (on embedding

intersectionality in health equity practice),² the 'UN Intersectionality Resource Guide and Toolkit' (on addressing intersectionality in policies and programmes) (UN Women, 2021), the 'Making It Work How-To Guide: Intersectionality in practice' (MIW, 2022), and the 'WHISE Intersectionality Guide' (WHISE, 2025). Still, as recently noted, '[in] existing research on intersectionality's operationalisation, there is little evidence of intersectionality actually being applied by policymakers as yet' (Christoffersen, 2023).

Against the above background, it is essential that we as a project elucidate the method by which we intend to translate our theoretical understanding of intersectionality into its practical application to the context of our pilot citizens' assemblies.

Essentially, there are four **key considerations** that have guided the process of turning our analytical and normative framework into practical application (Figure 4). Each of these key considerations were formed through the findings of the project so far, namely through the theoretical exploration of intersectionality and how it fits within both the literature on citizens' assemblies (Deliverable 2.2) and current citizens' assembly practices and evaluation techniques (Deliverable 3.3). The four considerations also function as safeguards against applied conceptions of intersectionality that risk hollowing out its critical edge. For instance, being explicit about the project's normative understanding of intersectionality (Key Consideration 1) ensures that we will keep power relations and structural marginalisation at the centre of our work. Sustained attention to our positionality (Key Consideration 2) resists the assumption that the team holds a neutral standpoint dislocated from intersecting structures of privilege and oppression. Adopting a context-based approach (Key Consideration 3) insists that membership of a social group and of the intersection of social groups is understood alongside an understanding of institutional, historical, and social structures rather than a matter solely of personal identities. Finally, the focus of the project on targeted interventions (Key Consideration 4) guides the adoption of considered design choices at the input, throughput, and output stages.

These considerations—which are interrelated and mutually reinforcing—are useful both in explaining the remit and scope of the pilots, and in illustrating the way in which intersectionality has infused all of our thinking so far, albeit that it will not be practicable within the confines of our

² Intersectionality Research Institute, The Intersectionality Policymaking Toolkit, available at: <https://intersectionality.gwu.edu/ipt>

project to design and implement *all* aspects of our pilot assemblies with explicit intersectionality features. The choice of designing ‘targeted interventions’ therefore forms a particularly important limb of our methodological approach to incorporating intersectionality into the pilot citizens’ assemblies. Our approach is further illustrated under each of the four considerations, below:

Figure 4. Key methodological considerations guiding the design of the EU-CIEMBLY pilots

We now turn to explain each of these considerations in turn, with the focus here in Deliverable 3.4 being on explaining ***what interventions we are planning to test*** and ***why those particular interventions***, while the focus in Deliverable 4.1 turns to explain ***how we are designing the pilots (across the input, throughput, and output categorising dimensions) to materialise these interventions.***

1. Be Explicit about our Normative Understanding of Intersectionality

The thrust of our discussion around intersectionality in Deliverable 2.2 was that there are many **theoretical conceptions** of intersectionality and many ways of **engaging** with intersectionality as a theoretical concept. Our conceptual or theoretical understanding of intersectionality is one that recognises the importance of power relations and structural marginalisation, but which also accepts the need to categorise social groups to meaningfully understand and engage with the idea of intersectional marginalisation, especially in the context of citizens' assemblies where demographics are used for the recruitment of participants to an assembly. It was also explained in Deliverable 2.2. that our method of engagement with intersectionality theory is to deploy it as an 'analytical' lens to: (1) foreground gaps in the application of intersectionality in the context of citizens' assemblies; and (2) devise solutions to mitigate those same gaps. This method of engaging with intersectionality theory has already been put to use in the evaluation of existing citizens' assembly practices in Deliverable 3.3. The present Deliverable 3.4 turns to explaining how intersectionality as a normative and analytical lens can be deployed in the design and delivery of our pilot citizens' assemblies with the goal of infusing the design and delivery of those pilot assemblies with the qualities of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation.

As noted above, there have long been difficulties associated with translating theoretical conceptions of intersectionality into practice. In now considering intersectionality as an 'applied' concept as this project does, it is essential that our theoretical and normative understanding of intersectionality influences our choice of applied intersectionality concepts and guides the design of our pilot citizens' assemblies. In other words, in thinking about intersectionality more practically than theoretically, it is important not to lose sight of the overarching normative goal of the project, which is to address intersectional exclusion and marginalisation understood as the product of overlapping power relations. This risk has been well-illustrated by Christoffersen (2021), a scholar working on the application or operationalisation of intersectionality in practice, who has identified various 'applied' conceptions of intersectionality in the existing practice of organisations in the third sector, i.e., in how organisations in the third sector (purport to) apply intersectionality in practice.³ This reminds us of the need for the project to ensure consistency between our practical

³ Although Christoffersen's research concerns the third sector, the findings of the research are directly relevant to us given the current lack of a similar study of any 'applied conception of intersectionality' in citizens' assemblies or deliberative mini-publics.

implementation of intersectionality concepts and our normative understanding of those same concepts.

The ‘applied’ approach that most closely aligns to our project’s normative understanding of intersectionality as set out in Deliverable 2.2 is described by Christoffersen as the ‘intersection of strands’ approach. This **intersection of strands** approach to applying intersectionality has to do with particular social groups sharing intersecting identities e.g., women of colour, without one strand being prioritised over the other. The intersection of strands approach has the benefit of not prioritising one characteristic or social group over another. **This approach most closely reflects our project’s theoretical and normative understanding of intersectionality in that it is ‘non-additive’.** As Christoffersen (2021, p. 24) explains ‘[t]his way of thinking about intersectionality recognises that structures of inequality are *always* intersecting, so no inequality can be separated out from others that together shape identity and experience’ and which includes elements of both privilege and disadvantage. However, as Christoffersen (2021) also notes, this approach does not *necessarily* consider the notion of ‘power relations’, which as we have already explained, is a key element of our normative conceptualisation of intersectionality.

Considering the above **applied** conceptualisations of intersectionality—and the links made with our project—means that we must be mindful of the extent to which our (indeed any) normative conceptualisation of intersectionality might be ‘undermined’ or ‘modified’ in its practical application, but also to strive to ensure that **power relations** *are* centred in the design, delivery, and evaluation of our pilot citizens’ assemblies. In other words, in the choice and design of targeted intersectional interventions discussed below, we should ensure that our application and operationalisation of intersectionality is guided by our normative and theoretical understanding of the same concept. In this process, compromises and trade-offs will be inevitable, as already recognised in Deliverable 2.2 and in our framework for intersectionality in citizens’ assemblies. This is especially so given that intersectionality is not a concept that has previously been operationalised in any specific way, to our knowledge, within the context of citizens’ assemblies.

Christoffersen (2021, p. 24) notes two additional challenges associated with the application of the intersection of strands approach that we should be mindful of, namely: (1) this approach has tended to focus on alleviating the symptoms, rather than addressing the causes of inequality; and (2) the difficulty of ‘meaningfully taking into account all markers of inequality’. As to the first challenge, the project’s approach to understanding and conceptualising intersectionality as an

analytical framework is to be deployed in: (1) better describing and understanding the problem of the exclusion of marginalised groups from citizens' assemblies; and (2) addressing and mitigating such exclusion. We also explained why the exclusion of diverse voices from citizens' assemblies is *problematic* both in and of itself, but also from the perspective of defining clear pathways for integrating intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation into citizens' assemblies.

As to the second challenge of not being able to account for all aspects of marginalisation, it was also argued in Deliverable 2.2 that practicality necessitates a narrowing of the focus of this—and indeed any—project seeking to apply or operationalise intersectionality as an analytical lens. In other words, there is a need to choose which social groups to focus on, hence the discussion of social groups in Deliverable 2.2 and our context-based approach described below. In any case, the application of intersectionality does necessitate the consideration of both **individual and structural dimensions** in that individual identities and perceptions are *shaped* by 'the synthesis of inequality structures' such as sexism or racism (Christoffersen, 2023 p. 3). In this way, there is no inherent contradiction in a focus on both identities and structures in that there is mutual reinforcement between the two. The context-based approach described below is key to understanding and expounding these individual and structural dimensions on a case-by-case basis.

2. Be Mindful of our own Positionality

We already emphasised in previous work in this project that, in adopting an intersectional approach to rethinking citizens' assemblies based on overlapping and interrelated power relations and marginalisation, we as a project team must be conscious of our own positionality.⁴ Intersectionality recognises that 'we all bring personal values, interests and beliefs based on our own unique lived experiences' (UN Women, 2021 p. 18). Therefore, reflecting on, and addressing, one's own power and subjectivity is a crucial step in any intersectional approach (UN Women, 2021). As a team composed largely of white, highly educated, Europe-based academics and professionals, we remain aware that we hold a relatively privileged position to others. In addition, and regardless of our individual positionality, we have also been explicit in adopting the concept of 'allyship' in our approach to researching intersectionality in citizens' assemblies, a concept

⁴ See Deliverable 2.2, v2 pp. 42–43.

grounded in solidarity and interconnected understanding between relatively privileged and relatively less privileged groups (Ajele & McGill, 2020 p. 36).

This emphasis on the positionality of ourselves as researchers has fed through the design of the pilots, in acknowledging the importance of positionality to the roles we are called to play in the project, whether as organisers, facilitators, or evaluators of the pilot citizens' assemblies.⁵ In addition, it has inspired one of the cross-cutting interventions that we seek to explore, namely the way in which *facilitation* of a citizens' assembly can be designed and organised along the lines of intersectional inclusion, equality, and good deliberation. Literature and practice explored so far in Deliverables 2.2 and 3.3 respectively has shown us that facilitation is key to addressing power imbalances, biases, and inequities during citizens' assembly processes. This insight has also largely been reflected in practical guides written by practitioners and researchers on organising and running citizens' assemblies (White et. al., 2022 pp. 58-63; DemocracyNext, 2023 p. 8-12; Innovation in Democracy, 2020).

We have also seen through our empirical research that intersectionality has not been explicitly considered in the practice of citizens' assemblies so far. This has led us to ask: how can facilitation be infused with more explicit considerations of intersectionality (including the creation of training materials for facilitators, and the preparation and facilitation of activities for the participants during the assembly)? As further explained below, this is one of the ideas that we wish to test across the three pilots. We intend to conduct a full positionality review at various stages of the design and rollout of the pilots to capture the positionality of the *project team*, *facilitators*, and *participants* through the lens of intersectionality and marginalisation.

3. Adopt a Context-Based Approach

In Deliverable 2.2, and based on the literature explored therein, we argued that the precise interaction between social groups and structures of marginalisation can only properly be understood **in context**, whether institutional, historical, or geographical. In other words, the concepts of exclusion, marginalisation or indeed intersectionality itself, can be dependent on the particular context, including the categorisation—and relationship between—social groups (McKinzie & Richards, 2018). We emphasised in particular the importance of context in the design

⁵ For examples of research on deliberative mini-publics that refers to the positionality of the researchers, see Curato & Calamba, 2024; Curato et al., 2023.

of citizens' assemblies given the notable differences between citizens' assemblies organised at a local, national, or transnational level as well as the related differences between top-down and bottom-up/community-led citizens' assemblies.

Context is also crucial regarding the choice of social groups selected as the focus of our research. In order for any specific intersectionality-oriented analysis to be meaningful, it is necessary to select a number of social groups or 'establish anchor points as a strategic choice' (Christensen & Jensen, 2012 p. 112). The choice of these groups depends on what is deemed most important for a specific research question at a specific time (Christensen & Jensen, 2012). **We have made a strategic choice to emphasise in our project racial or ethnic origin; sex or gender; age or generation; and socio-economic status as our anchor social groups.**⁶ As explained in Deliverable 2.2, this approach goes beyond the project's initial focus on sex and age which had been provided as an illustrative case study. The findings outlined in Deliverable 2.2 concluded that a narrow focus on only two axes would not adequately capture the structural and power-based dimensions of intersectional marginalisation. The selected social groups derive from the existing literature on the theory and practice of intersectionality and also represent the primary and well-established axes of social stratification used in sociological research. We have also argued that precisely what is meant by these social groups, and who precisely is marginalised within those social groups, needs to be adapted to the local, national, and transnational context.

In its application in practice, this context-based analysis will not simply look at these four anchor social groups in isolation. Rather, its purpose is to identify the *specific intersections* of these groups that constitute the relevant persons belonging to multiple intersecting marginalised groups (PMIMG) in the given polity, **in relation to the pilots' topic of housing**. This is seen as a first step in understanding the wider (structural, societal, and legal) systems of power, including vis-a-vis traditional democratic mechanisms. An example of how this can be achieved is by conducting a 'power analysis' of the given context. A power analysis allows for the consideration of who holds the power in a particular community and, crucially, how that power can be shifted (Ayles, 2025 p. 13). A power analysis serves as a useful structuring device for applying our intersectional normative framework to understand intersectional marginalisation in a given context, as well as allowing us to navigate the relevant decision-makers and policy influencers.

⁶ See Deliverable 2.2, v2, Section V. p. 83–106.

4. Choose Targeted Interventions that can have a Positive Impact on Current Practices

We are not looking to design the perfect citizens' assembly or to replace the way in which citizens' assemblies are currently taking place. In other words, we are not seeking to create an 'intersectional citizens' assembly' that will overhaul the entirety of current practices. We have shown in Deliverable 2.2 that an intersectional approach serves to foreground the unique challenges, needs, experiences, and knowledge of marginalised individuals within the context of citizens' assemblies. **Our goal, therefore, is to offer a feasible approach to embedding intersectionality in the deliberative process that takes place in citizens' assemblies.**

Overall, the pilots seek to provide the team with findings that can then be turned into recommendations and suggestions primarily for three groups of stakeholders. First, to anyone who, like us, acknowledges the added value of adopting an intersectional lens to understanding and addressing power imbalances in citizens' assemblies. This may include researchers and practitioners who are interested in designing, implementing, and evaluating more inclusive citizens' assemblies and are looking for ways to embed such an intersectional lens in their practices. Second, to law-makers and policy-makers who might be looking either to further utilise the potential of citizens' assemblies as citizens' participation forums and/or who are looking to codify or formalise citizens' assemblies. And, third, to citizens, citizens' groups, and CSOs that wish to explore the possibility of organising and holding their own citizens' assemblies or citizens' assembly-like mechanisms (e.g., other types of deliberative mini-publics) whether at the local, national, or transnational level.

At the same time, as a research project, we have some inherent limitations that do not allow for all optimal design choices to be tested in all the pilots. Although in an ideal world, with unlimited funds that allow the use of multiple possible strategies for engagement, intersectionality-driven considerations should guide all the design choices made for all stages of an assembly, we have made the strategic choice **to test specific, targeted interventions** that we have developed for each of our three pilots. This was seen to fit better the scope and character of the EU-CIEMBLY project, acknowledging that our pilots are inevitably different than real-life citizens' assemblies that are initiated e.g., by a commissioning authority, are mandated by law, employ professional actors, and which work with a much larger budget and resources than us. This approach also makes feasible the task of testing various interventions and drawing conclusions as to whether

those could become meaningful additions to existing practices and/or that inspire targeted changes in the way citizens' assemblies are currently taking place. Moreover, this approach seeks to ensure the 'accessibility' of our recommendations across various types and levels of citizens' assemblies, including those that are bottom-up or community-led.

Each of the three pilots is focused on **one main intervention** that aims to translate intersectionality considerations into practice, while the project implements in parallel **a cross-cutting intervention** regarding facilitation. Even though we might have been unable to implement all possible design choices that could cater to intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation, given limited time and funds, all the planned interventions derive from our understanding of intersectionality *and* have been designed with intersectionality in mind.

Having said that, the targeted nature of our planned interventions does not take away from their **ambition**: for example, both the context-based approach and the more prominent role for intersectionality in the facilitation process (regarding its design and the training provided to facilitators, as well as activities with the participants during the pilots) are capable of having a significant positive impact on the current practice surrounding citizens' assemblies.

IV. Targeted Intersectional Interventions

After setting out the key considerations that have informed the work on the pilot assemblies so far, the discussion in this section proceeds to describe the targeted intersectional interventions that we are planning to conduct.

As we previously mentioned, the design of the pilots was informed by the six theoretical models that were developed in Deliverable 2.3. Some of those models were more closely relied on for the macro design of specific pilots, while other models informed our work more indirectly. In particular, and as we explain further below under each pilot, the ideas and suggestions put forward in the Power Sharing Model (Model 4) have formed the basis for the local pilot design, those in the Descriptive and Discursive Representation models (Models 1 and 2) have informed the design of the national pilot, and those in the Subaltern Counterpublics Model (Model 4) have provided the source of inspiration for the design of the transnational pilot. While the pilots take inspiration from these models, they do not seek to follow them to the letter; in any case, Deliverable 2.2 itself states that the models are not an off-the-shelf solution for this later stage of the project.

Starting from the above models for the macro design of each pilot was a deliberate choice we made based on the general parameters of each pilot, our research objectives, as well as the context in which each pilot will take place. The following section expounds on how each model was used as the starting point for thinking of the respective pilot, as well as why we choose to start from these models in the macro design of each pilot. It should also be noted that, while the Agonistic Pluralism Model (Model 5) and the Relationality and Interdependence Model (Model 6) did not explicitly provide the basis for one of the pilots, they both have a role to play in the pilots' design. For instance, Model 6 has informed the cross-cutting intervention of facilitation, which is illustrated in Section V, and Model 5 will be further considered during the micro-design phase as it relates more closely to the throughput design stage of an assembly. Figure 5 illustrates:

Figure 5. The relationship between the Deliverable 2.3 models and the pilots' design

The subsequent discussion provides first an overview of the design parameters characterising all three pilots before discussing in more detail each pilot separately.

1. The Overall Parameters for the Three Pilot Citizens' Assemblies

Between October 2025 and January 2026, the project team will be engaged in the design, implementation, and evaluation of three pilot citizens' assemblies. Each of the three pilots fit a different level of governance: one pilot will take place locally, one will take place nationally, and one will take place transnationally. The **number of participants** in each pilot is adjusted to the pilot's territorial scope while remaining within the scale of participants that tend to constitute a citizens' assembly: our aim is that the local assembly will consist of 50 participants; the national assembly will consist of 75 participants, and the transnational assembly will consist of 100 participants. This will allow us to assess the impact of the group's size on embedding intersectionality considerations in the design and practice of an assembly.

Each pilot will be essentially organised around **the three typical stages of a citizens' assembly**: (1) a plenary session where participants meet each other and engage with information regarding the scope of the assembly; (2) small working groups during which the participants discuss the topic and produce their findings; (3) and a final plenary session where they reach their final decisions. Pre-meeting and in-between meeting activities or tasks in various formats will also be considered for each pilot. This will include online digital participation activities facilitated by the

project partner Make.org, which seek to open up the topics of the pilot citizens' assemblies to the broader world and expand input beyond the group of participants that will be in the room.

Regarding the pilots' **locations**, the local pilot will take place at Colchester, Essex, UK and online. The national pilot will take place in Cyprus and online and, to our knowledge, it will be the first citizens' assembly of its kind that will take place in the country.⁷ The transnational pilot will be hosted online with participants from EU Member States. A combination of face-to-face and online activities will take place for the local and the national pilot, while the transnational pilot will take place entirely online, allowing us to explore the opportunities and limitations of hosting an assembly in hybrid and online fora, from an intersectionality point of view and in light of the recent focus on the use of digital participation platforms and on the spatial qualities of designing citizens' assemblies (Redman & Cramers, 2020; People Powered, 2025; Nielsen & MacDonald-Nelson, 2025), and taking into consideration the findings of our empirical research in Deliverable 3.3.

Finally, the **broad topic** of the assemblies was chosen to reflect issues that are of concern to citizens' day-to-day life, and which fit the location, timing, and duration of each pilot as well as the focus of the project on intersectionality. With regard to the latter, for example, the team reflected during a series of team meetings on whether the three assemblies should revolve around the same topic and/or whether there was a particular aspect of a topic that might affect less privileged social groups more than privileged groups. These kinds of conversations were guided by a context-based approach (Key Consideration 3).

For instance, acknowledging that we are likely more privileged than persons belonging to the intersection of marginalised groups, we sought evidence through publicly available data on topic areas that would allow us to start thinking about current issues that affect people whose voices might not be heard otherwise.

We also approached the pilot assemblies as an opportunity to engage the participants in a topic that is currently not yet being widely discussed and raised in other traditional participatory fora. Starting from a list of potential topics, we discarded those that had already benefited from being the subject of other citizens' assemblies, such as climate change, those that were narrowly

⁷ An assembly of a smaller scale took place online in 2024 as part of a project named U-SOLVE: <https://www.ucy.ac.cy/usolve/participation-in-citizens-assembly/> accessed 9 October 2025.

relevant to only one pilot, such as street safety for the local pilot, and those that were too extensive to be covered within the contours of our pilots, such as the cost-of-living crisis. We also took into consideration the knowledge that sits within members of the project team, who will have the primary responsibility of further framing the topic and creating relevant materials for the assembly.

In line with our key intersectionality consideration of adopting a **context-based approach**, one of the factors that we took into account in selecting the broad topic of each pilot was to identify and understand the **broader political landscape** in the environment in which the pilots would take place. To provide examples, when designing the local pilot at Colchester we had in mind that the pilot would take place in the run-up to the Essex Mayoral elections in Spring of 2026 and thus we selected a topic with potential to be addressed by the Mayor as the relevant powerholder and potential recipient of the recommendations of the assembly, thus giving a platform for the consideration of the assembly work. Similarly, the Cyprus pilot will take place in the run-up to the parliamentary elections and during the Cyprus Presidency of the Council of the European Union, which could make the political climate more receptive than usual to testing out novel forms of citizens' participation, such as a nation-wide citizens' assembly. There is also currently rising interest around citizens' participation in Cyprus. In his second annual review message for 2025, the Cypriot president announced: '[a]fter all, our goal is participatory democracy; the participation of everyone, institutional and social partners, political forces, and first and foremost, the Cypriot people in the great effort to reform our country' (Republic of Cyprus, 2025). A newly launched online platform 'εκφραCY' (which translates into 'expression'), enables a two-way communication between young people and the Executive, while a new 'Citizen's Voice' platform conducts advisory votes.

Regarding the transnational pilot, we wanted to select a topic of broad potential interest to the EU population and with clear ways in which recommendations could feed into EU law-making and policy-making processes. Our thinking process started from the fact that transnational citizens' assemblies are not common practice across Europe and do not take place frequently. As stated in Participedia, '[a] relatively recent addition to the deliberative democracy sphere, transnational citizens' assemblies respond to nuanced issues that transcend borders. They bring together individuals from multiple nations and exhibit similar characteristics to traditional citizens'

assemblies.⁸ This means that our pilot has the potential to make a novel contribution, but the boundaries of that contribution need to be clearly distinguished. We were particularly alert to the current assembly-like practice of European Citizens' Panels in the EU, which we studied as part of Deliverable 3.3, and thus we decided to think of the transnational pilot alongside the Panels.

With the above in mind, we identified **housing** as a tangible issue that affects everyone at some level. To be clear, by setting the topic we do not mean preventing the topic of the assembly from eventually being adjusted by participants later in the process (depending on the governance model of each pilot), or by stakeholders e.g., via the co-design process described for the local pilot. Instead, we refer to the framing of the assembly's **remit**, itself an 'input' phase design choice that needed to be made in parallel to thinking about recruitment and output, from the early stages of the pilots' design. Indeed, there are several approaches possible when selecting housing as the underlying concern of the assemblies, therefore moments of co-creation will be essential to align the specific topic or topics to be discussed with the overall intersectional purposes of the assemblies.

Against this background, all pilots will relate to the topic of **housing** which is of common interest to all three levels in which our pilots will take place.

Regarding the **local pilot** at Colchester, the next section explains that the project will engage with the local community through collaboration with Citizens UK and Citizens Essex, a people-powered alliance, which works with a method of participation called **community organising**. Citizens UK's method of community organising focuses on bringing together a broad range of organisations, including schools, universities, faith communities, charities, trade unions and community organisations to work on a broad range of issues that impact individuals and communities (Citizens UK, 2025). Through relationship-building, Citizens UK brings communities together to develop campaigns and meet with power-holders, getting members of the community a 'seat at [the] decision-making table' and challenging traditional power structures. By collaborating with Citizens UK, the project will engage with a chapter of Citizens UK that has been active since 2019, bringing the team members' years of experience into the local pilot through co-design and participation in the assembly.

⁸ Participedia Collection: Transnational Citizens' Assemblies, available at: <https://participedia.net/collection/8376> accessed 9 October 2025.

Additionally, Citizens UK has a history of campaigning on issues related to housing. Housing and homelessness formed one of Citizens UK's nine focus areas in the build-up to the 2024 General Election in the UK (Citizens UK, 2024). In its manifesto, Citizens UK called on the next UK government to 'end child homelessness', 'unlock the potential for more affordable housing across the UK' and 'publish a national home upgrade strategy which will make our existing homes safe and healthy as well as more energy-efficient' (Citizens UK, 2024 p. 23). Citizens Essex has had previous success on collaborative housing campaigns, expanding the Malachi Homes project in 2022, which provided 'quality modular housing for people experiencing homelessness' (Citizens UK, 2024, p. 22; Salvation Army, 2022). Currently, Citizens Essex is focused on organising across Essex for the first Mayoral election which will be held in May 2026 (Citizens Essex, 2025); a process in which our pilot assembly hopes to provide input.

As part of wider national plans from the Labour government to rebalance power regionally in England, devolution in Greater Essex will reform local government and establish a Mayoral Combined County Authority, bringing together Essex County Council, Southend-on-Sea City Council and Thurrock Council (Essex County Council, 2025). The new authority will be led by a directly elected mayor with the first elections taking place in May 2026. The devolution plan, as set out in the Devolution Framework in the English Devolution White Paper (2024), includes mayoral responsibility for 'strategically planning for housing growth' to deliver housing closer to infrastructure and more social and affordable housing. Accordingly, housing is not only a topic of immediate concern to the community, but also an area where we will have the opportunity, through the pilot, to contribute to public decision-making around the subject.

Regarding the **national pilot**, there is a growing housing crisis in Cyprus that strains residents' access to affordable homes. Because demand is generally higher than supply, competition among renters has grown, making the search for suitable housing more difficult (Cyprus Mail, 2025). The Minister for the Interior noted in March 2025 that rising interest rates and strong demand from foreign workers, which results from regional geopolitical tensions, have increased construction costs and restricted supply, further reducing housing access for local residents.⁹ This is echoed by the UN-Habitat chief, who noted in a recent interview that '[f]or smaller countries like Cyprus,

⁹ As explained by the Cyprus Interior Minister in March 2025, during the Cyprus Land Development Conference. <https://www.philenews.com/oikonomia/kypros/article/1567772/schedia-stegasis-1-900-nees-katikies-stin-agera/> accessed 9 October 2025.

the housing crisis often feels more acute due to the limited housing stock, restricted suitable land availability, greater import dependence, and constrained public budgets that complicate large-scale affordable housing provision' (Tourki, 2025). The importance of the issue of housing in Cyprus was highlighted both through conversations with our local project partner, ASPON, as well as through conversations that our project team has had with local NGOs and government officials.

The topic of housing in Cyprus also presents interest from an intersectionality perspective. For instance, families with children are facing significant strains in securing affordable accommodation due to the fact that rental increases are not met by their median salary income (Kóκκινος, 2025). In a report from 2025, the NGO Cyprus Refugee Council noted that there are no governmental schemes providing housing to refugees (beneficiaries of international protection), who are facing barriers and financial constraints related to high levels of unemployment, high rent prices, reluctance of landlords to rent premises to non-EU citizens and the sufficiency of given allowances in securing private accommodation (Cyprus Refugee Council, 2025).

Finally, regarding the **transnational, EU-based pilot**, housing is a priority of the EU. It is high on the agenda of the European Parliament, which established a Special Committee to deal with the EU's Housing Crisis, and which is expected to conclude its work in December 2025, potentially allowing us to draw on that work for the purposes of the pilots. Housing is also high on the agenda of priorities of the European Commission, with the Commission President declaring in her Political Guidelines that '[w]e urgently need to address the housing crisis facing millions of families and young people' and appointing a new Commissioner for Energy and Housing (European Parliament, 2024). The remit of the newly-appointed Commissioner, Dan Jørgensen, is to support Member States in addressing the root causes of housing supply issues and to unlock public and private investment for affordable and sustainable housing, and the EU is currently preparing to put forward its first-ever European Affordable Housing Plan.

From an **intersectionality point of view**, housing is a topic that is highly relevant to marginalised communities, including migrants, racialised people, LGBTQ+ people, people with disabilities, and those with insecure immigration status, who are more likely to experience homelessness or housing insecurity, overcrowded or unsafe living conditions, and discrimination in the housing market. What is more, it is a topic that has been approached in the research from an intersectionality perspective. 'Housing intersectionality' is used as a term to 'explore simultaneously multiple social identities – such as race, gender, income, disability, age, and

immigration status – and how they interact to shape people’s access to safe, affordable, and secure housing. (...) Intersectional housing analysis moves beyond one-size-fits-all solutions. It also underscores the need for inclusive housing policy that actively addresses overlapping vulnerabilities’ (Dunning & Moore, 2025). This kind of research will help us to consider embedding in the throughput stage of the assemblies themselves materials and perspectives on intersectionality in housing. In this way, the concept of housing intersectionality weds the project’s theoretical focus (intersectionality) with its practical application (housing), providing a solid foundation for the learning and deliberation stages of the pilot citizens’ assemblies.

Beyond the relevance of the topic of housing for all three levels of governance in which the pilots will take place, having the same broad topic for the three pilots will further allow us to research the dimension of **‘scaling up’** an assembly from the local, to the national, and to the transnational level. How do we adapt the assembly materials to match the growing complexity of issues from the community level to government level and then to EU law-making? And, what challenges and opportunities does this create when trying to integrate intersectionality into citizens’ assembly design?

Figure 6: Framing the broad topics of the three pilots

The above discussion on housing as the topic for the assemblies is not meant to be exhaustive. There are more detailed design choices to be taken regarding the dimension of the topic that will be explored in each pilot, and Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2 will provide this type of detail as we move on with designing our pilots at a more granular level. For now, the subsequent discussion moves to a central point of this report, which is to explain our approach of targeted (intersectional) interventions by pilot, followed by an explanation of our plan to explore how to embed intersectionality in the facilitation stage of all three pilots.

2. Targeted Interventions by Pilot

Within the above general parameters of how the pilots were envisioned and considering the series of potential choices and trade-offs for operationalising intersectionality in citizens' assemblies which were presented in Deliverable 2.3, we have made the strategic choice to test the following targeted interventions in each pilot.

2.1. The Local Pilot: Power Sharing and Co-Designing through Community Engagement

For the local pilot, which will take place in Colchester, we have taken inspiration from the Power Sharing Model of Deliverable 2.3 (pp. 38-43), which seeks to harness the power of a bottom-up approach to designing and conducting citizens' assemblies. The Power Sharing Model starts from the premise that members of marginalised groups or PMIMG have less power in society and less power when participating in citizens' assemblies across all phases than people belonging to relatively more privileged social groups. This consideration is especially apparent in the agenda-setting (input) stage of a citizens' assembly: having lesser power means PMIMG have fewer opportunities to shape or participate in the governance, formation, and terms of reference of citizens' assemblies. The idea advanced in Deliverable 2.3 was that a citizens' assembly could include elements of co-design and community governance in which PMIMG representatives have the authority to set the agenda and establish the rules of engagement. In particular, it was suggested that community advisors should have a role in the *input phase* of the citizens' assembly design.

The Power Sharing Model as explained in Deliverable 2.3 seeks to emphasise intersectional equality and to maximise intersectional inclusion by embedding a bottom-up or community-led approach to the design stage of an assembly, particularly regarding the design features of governance and management. The core idea is then that, by embedding such inclusive governance and management, the deliberation process itself becomes more intersectionality-oriented because the process for designing a citizens' assembly is better adapted to the community's needs.

Building on the above foundation, the local pilot aims to adopt a bottom-up, community-led approach to citizens' assembly design, aiming to address systemic power imbalances.

In a departure from a strictly demographically representative approach to recruitment, the pilot seeks to bring together two different communities within the space of the assembly: the University of Essex student community, and the local residents' community. It does so both by recruiting from these communities but also, and crucially, by involving the voice of these communities in the design phase. Here, the students are not seen as a distinct body of persons, but ultimately as part of the local community of Colchester, where the University campus is located. The rationale underpinning the choice of communities to engage in the pilot assembly process is to assess the ways in which an (intersectionality-oriented) citizens' assembly can contribute to the bridging of potential divides within wider communities and to explore commonalities of experience between them.

The pre-assembly co-design workshops seek to bring in, and learn from, representatives of these communities, namely representatives from the University of Essex Students' Union (SU), and representatives from Citizens Essex, which is a Citizens UK chapter with years of engagement with community-led practices. In particular, Citizens UK is a community organising charity, based in England and Wales, comprising eighteen regional chapters. Drawing on the work of Saul Alinsky (1989), the Citizens UK approach to community organising is rooted in broad-based organising, bringing together a wide and varied range of organisations to challenge hegemonic structures by building relationships and developing leaders (Wood, 2023). The chapter of Citizens UK in Essex was formed in 2019, with the founding of Colchester Citizens of which the University of Essex was a founding member. Since then, the University of Essex has continued to be a

strategic member of Citizens Essex, working as part of the local alliance to contribute to campaigns and deliver community organising training to students and staff.

Within the University, the Students' Union brings together all of the students at the University of Essex in one community. Each student at the University automatically becomes a member of the Essex SU, creating a community of 13,000 students across the campuses. The Students' Union is a charity that receives funding from the University, but it is recognised as a separate body that represents students. It is run by elected Student Leaders who are supported by permanent staff members. In addition to the elected Student Leaders, students are also represented by elected voluntary members of the SU Council and Student Community Officers. Each year the incoming Student Leader team reviews a wide range of feedback from students to set out their strategic plan for the upcoming academic year, called 'the Big Plan' (University of Essex Students' Union, 2025). The Big Plan for 2025/26 includes: Ensuring Affordable Food Options; Enhancing Support Pathways, Elevating Student-Led Events; Building Stronger Cohorts and Strengthening Inclusivity.

Through two co-design sessions, we aim to build a bottom-up, participatory process, engaging representatives of both the Students' Union and Citizens Essex. Representatives will be selected depending on their role within their organisation and their experience. The representatives will include, for example, individuals from the Students' Union who are elected to represent marginalised groups, or those who have been involved in campaigns on issues around housing, or whose work engages with the topic of housing. One of the co-design sessions will take place with representatives from the Students' Union and one with representatives from Citizens Essex. These will be held remotely (online) and in the evening, to avoid conflicts with work and studies.

Participants in the co-design workshops will be actively involved in the co-design of the pilots, engaging in a dialogue with the project team as assembly organisers to make decisions on key design features of the pilot collaboratively. The co-design sessions will be primarily discussion-based. While some of the design features are pre-determined due to the nature of the project, such as the location, number of sessions, broad topic and populations to be invited as participants, there are many key design choices to be determined through the co-design process. As such, the objectives of the co-design sessions will be: (1) to determine the framing of the topic of the local pilot; (2) to agree inclusion goals and recruitment channels across intersections; (3) to define approaches to shared lived experience and testimony (including safeguarding); and, (4) to map

pathways to impact through outputs and outcomes. To achieve this, each session will first give a brief overview of the EU-CIEMBLY project and the position of the local pilot before delving into discussions around key design choices such as the framing of the topic, recruitment and sampling, ground rules for the pilot, suggested outputs and outcomes and how to best achieve them.

Addressing power imbalances in the context of the local pilot therefore takes two forms: first, by embedding *bottom-up* elements to the citizens' assembly design at the *input stage*; and second, by engaging with and challenging the powerholders at the *output stage*. Based on community organising methodology, Citizens UK builds solidarity through shared lived experience to build relational power and engage power holders (Warren et al., 2024). One of the methods for engaging and challenging power holders is the 'accountability assembly' where power holders are invited to listen to the 'asks' of the community and to commit to change. Described as 'democratic theatres', accountability assemblies are designed to 'make visible the way powerholders are connected to communities' (Warren et al., 2024). The assembly is organised by the community and hosted in community-based institutions to bring together the broad base of institutions that work together to speak directly to those with power. This 'broad base' includes a wide range of institutions, including schools, colleges and universities, as well as religious institutions such as churches, synagogues, and mosques, and CSOs such as foodbanks and other related charities. The accountability assembly is crucially informed by in-depth listening exercises with the community, research into the responsibilities of authoritative bodies, and careful event planning by the community to ensure that those most affected by the topic or problem in question are given space to share their experience and to allow for response from those in positions of power.

Members of our team at the University of Essex have been collaborating and working with Citizens Essex and Citizens UK more broadly since 2018. This has involved collaboration on the delivery of community organising training through modules, developing campaigns with students and involvement in local campaigns. Campaigns have focused on topics such as violence against women and girls, migrant justice, the real living wage, provision of public transport, and housing (University of Essex, 2024). As members of the Colchester Citizens Alliance and the local chapter in Essex we have also attended strategic meetings, supported local actions as part of ongoing campaigns and worked closely with other local organisations to develop campaigns including churches, schools, and civil society organisations. This involvement erodes the traditional

distinction between 'researcher', 'teacher', and 'activist' and builds a solid base for collaboration through shared values and solidarity on issues impacting the local community.

Through the co-design methodology and collaboration with Citizens Essex, **community organising** will be used as a mechanism of organisation and of accountability. On the one hand, as a mechanism for organisation, the methods of community organising that will be used for the co-design workshops will ensure that the eventual pilot is designed with the input of stakeholders who are close to the communities and the dimensions of the topic that concern them. On the other hand, as a mechanism for accountability, community organising can help to ensure that the recommendations from the local pilot are followed up through Citizens Essex Mayoral Election Assembly which will be held in March 2026, where the recommendations of the local pilot will be presented to candidates from the major political parties. Built on the same principle as the 'accountability assembly' described above, the mayoral assembly will present 'asks' to candidates and ask for their commitment to work together with Citizens Essex on the issues raised.

An example of this model can be seen in the Citizens UK's General Election Assembly, where Citizens UK brought together 2,000 members to present their asks to representatives from the then major political parties and gain commitments to work on issues such as the living wage for social care workers and fair pathways to citizenship (Revault d'Allones, 2024). One of the key pledges made at this event was by Angela Rayner, who became Deputy Prime Minister (July 2024-September 2025), who committed to fight 'to give carers a real Living Wage' (Revault d'Allones, 2024). While there have been changes to government structures since then, Citizens UK are committed to the campaign and finding alternative routes to reach power holders, such as engaging regional mayors to urge the government to make change (Khan, 2025). As shown in this example, the collaboration with Citizens Essex on the local pilot ensures that the recommendations are handed to an organisation which has the ability to 'follow up' and can find alternative routes, if needed, to campaign for change.

The importance of the 'follow-up' and accountability was stressed by the interviews analysed in Deliverable 3.3 but is often beyond the scope of commissioned citizens' assemblies. Collaboration with Citizens Essex for the local pilot, therefore, ensures both the **input** of the involved communities in the design of the assembly and the potential for continuing relationships with powerholders and offers **opportunities** for the individuals to stay engaged with the process after it has officially ended, to push recommendations forward. In addition to the fact that members of

our team already have close ties with the community via their years long collaboration with Citizens UK, Citizens UK and Citizens Essex themselves have a history of campaigning on issues related to housing, as this was detailed in the previous section of this report. The focus of the local pilot on issues surrounding housing will directly feed into the remit of the new mayor and we will be able to share the recommendations resulting from the pilot through the Citizens Essex Mayoral Assembly which is scheduled to take place in March 2026.

To ensure this process secures genuine political uptake, the micro-design phase (Deliverable 4.1) will aim to operationalise this 'Power Sharing' model with a key output. Modelled on successful community organising tactics, the co-design team will work to secure a public, verbal commitment from all major candidates in the 2026 Mayoral election at the Citizens Essex Mayoral Assembly in March 2026. This commitment would bind the eventual winner to work with the Citizens Essex to make the recommendations a reality and to meet regularly with representatives of the local alliance to provide updates on the progress towards these goals. While this may ultimately prove unsuccessful, we think it is important to try to create a concrete, post-election accountability loop that institutionalises the pilot's influence.

2.2. The National Pilot: Descriptive and Discursive Representation through Intersectionality-Informed Recruitment and Content

For the national pilot, which will take place in Cyprus, we started from the idea inherent in the Descriptive Representation model of Deliverable 2.3 (pp. 13-19) that the assembly be reflective of a wider community. This approach can be constructed on the basis of **variations to sortition** as explained throughout the interviews we conducted and assessed as part of Deliverable 3.3. Such potential variations or supplements to sortition include: (1) over-representing a particular demographic group (e.g., young people); (2) setting quotas for including specific demographics; or (3) focusing recruitment efforts on engaging 'hard to reach' participants.¹⁰ Both targeted outreach and relationship building were highlighted in the interviews as ways to supplement the more conventional lottery recruitment process (see Deliverable 3.3 Recommendations I2 and I4, p. 148). These observations raise the question of whether the standard method of sortition, which has been considered the 'gold standard' of recruitment, could be supplemented or modified in a

¹⁰ For a recent helpful explanation of various ways to recruit in deliberative mini-publics see Ercan et al., 2025.

way that is more explicitly linked to intersectional inclusion and equality. According to the Descriptive Representation model of Deliverable 2.3, this could be done by having people from the intersections of specific, marginalised, social groups being represented by participants in the room who also belong to the same intersections. One way in which that model suggested that this could be done was by selecting the relevant social groups, finding their representation in the population, alongside the intersections between these groups. The next step would be to ensure that each intersection is represented in the citizens' assembly, regardless of the size of the intersection between each group.

However, the Descriptive Representation model, as discussed in Deliverable 2.3, entails several challenges. These include the risk of tokenism where the socio-demographic categories are broken down into such a level of granularity that, in a relatively small group of people, only one or two are PMIMG. In addition, there is a risk of essentialising participants by assuming that someone from the intersection of social groups will represent others from that intersection. In fact, this assumption sits uneasily with intersectionality theory, which posits that intersectionality does not merely involve the combination of identity categories to analyse another group's experience (Cho et al., 2013).¹¹ Another limitation outlined in Deliverable 2.3 is (wrongly) assuming that PMIMG will always represent a minority group's interest. Making such an assumption overlooks other important factors, such as communicative barriers, power asymmetries, and structural constraints, that shape who is able to speak, how, and with what authority.

Taking stock of these limitations, we considered as the inspiration for the national pilot a combination of the Descriptive Representation and the Discursive Representation models from Deliverable 2.3. According to the Discursive Representation model, the inclusion of diverse knowledge, perspectives, and discourses of people from the intersection of multiple marginalised social groups can become the basis for a more intersectionality-oriented assembly. The Discursive Representation model proposes the design of mechanisms that enable the representation of collective voice through the inclusion of advocates in the assembly, i.e., individuals nominated to represent a specific group or articulate their perspectives during deliberation. This inclusion of advocates can take place in various ways, either by designating a portion of the assembly for targeted recruitment that will be filled by representatives from various CSOs, or by giving a platform to those CSOs as experts or witnesses to the assembly.

¹¹ From Deliverable 2.2, pp. 39-40.

We are interested in exploring whether and how the two approaches (one related to recruitment and one related to the information-providing throughput stage of the assembly) can be combined in practice to provide an alternative way of ensuring intersectionality-oriented internal and external inclusion.

As such, we will consider the relationship between traditional sortition-based recruitment and sampling methods and the potential need to introduce innovative or additional methods to address intersectionality considerations. We will therefore use the Cyprus census as a **starting point** to maintain a link between our assembly and the concept of demographic representation among the participants, also bearing in mind that any recruitment method should be alert to the underlying historical and social context without which recruitment innovations can become a blunt instrument. We will then conduct a context-based analysis to identify who is marginalised at the intersection of the project's anchor social groups (ethnicity/race; sex/gender, age/generation, and socio-economic background) in light of historical, structural, and legal obstacles as they relate to the topic of the assembly—in our case problems around housing in Cyprus. This analysis will feed back into making our sampling and recruitment decisions on how the 75 'seats' of the assembly are to be filled.

One option, for instance, would be a quota system informed by the above context-based analysis, whereby a portion of the assembly comes from the 'majority' or '(relatively) privileged' groups, and a portion comes from PMIMG. This intervention will be based on a flexible 'quota system' which is not uncommon in the practice of citizens' assemblies. Some of our interviewees, for example, already referred to the practice of including participants from a particular demographic group into the potential sample pool, a practice often referred to as 'oversampling'.¹² The difference with our approach is that we would be looking to explore the potential of oversampling and recruiting persons into the citizens' assembly who belong at the intersection of multiple marginalised groups.

Another option that we will explore is the possibility to recruit in the assembly a sufficiently diverse group of participants without necessarily looking explicitly to recruit at the intersections. Instead, we would look to embed intersectionality considerations **during the assembly itself**, e.g., by inviting CSO advocates and other actors that operate close to the Cyprus society and who have

¹² Deliverable 3.3 p. 36.

connections and relations with people belonging to the intersection of marginalised groups, whose profiles would not have appeared in any census or official governmental statistics otherwise. Those CSO advocates would then be asked to contribute to the information-providing *throughput* stage of the assembly and specifically to contribute the perspectives of persons belonging to the intersection of social groups in relation to the topic of the assembly itself, e.g., with a discussion, reflection, or a presentation of the challenges faced by young, migrant workers in securing affordable housing in Cyprus.

In this way, we will seek to embed in the pilot mechanisms that enable the representation of intersectional experiences **through the inclusion of advocates in the throughput stages**. As mentioned above, this can take the form of life experience stories by representatives from Civil Society Organisations who are close to the marginalised communities or who have experience in working with the topic of intersectional marginalisation in Cyprus. It will also take the form of including material in the assembly that presents the intersectional dimensions of the housing problem. We will do this while remaining alert to: (1) the risks of ‘tokenism’; (2) the position that an individual assembly participant does not act as a representative of the views of other people belonging to the intersection of the same social groups; and (3) our context-based approach, whereby the context of the assembly is used to define which social groups’ intersections are the most marginalised vis-a-vis democratic participation opportunities in Cyprus more generally speaking.

What is more, in both of the alternative options mentioned here we will also remain alert to considerations and trade-offs raised in Deliverable 2.3. These refer, for example, to the need to balance a focus on how many PMIMG are included in the room (external inclusion) with equally weighted attention to how the deliberation is handled while in the room (internal inclusion). A PMIMG quota model will be assessed for its impact on internal inclusion compared to a more ‘conventional’ diverse sample that is complemented by discursive representation via CSOs. The approach to the national pilot design described here leaves open the possibility of testing different aspects at the evaluation stage, including: (a) whether more intersectionality attuned recruitment can be achieved under real-world constraints; (b) testing whether discursive representation through CSO advocates and expert selection changes the content and tone of deliberation; or (c) probing the tensions between the two.

In adhering to a context-based approach and needing to be mindful of our own positionality (and of what we *do not know* about the lives of those in less privileged positions than us), the project team will engage with Cyprus-based CSOs and other stakeholders, including public officials such as the Cyprus Commissioner for the Citizen and the Cyprus Commissioner for Gender Equality, to map and understand marginalisation and intersectionality regarding housing issues in Cyprus. It is our contention that such communication with Cyprus-based actors is necessary to further specify the recruitment and selection methods of the assembly and to assess whether it is, indeed, possible to combine intersectionality-oriented input stage choices (i.e., sampling and recruitment) with intersectionality-oriented throughput stage choices (i.e., choice of experts and materials).

Close communication with Cyprus-based organisations is feasible largely because the project team includes a partner organisation that is based in Cyprus (ASPON Consulting), and one of the University of Essex (WP4 leader) researchers is originally from Cyprus. The knowledge that these partners possess in relation to the location, society, and political and legal context of Cyprus is one of the reasons why Cyprus was chosen for the national pilot assembly. Furthermore, the closeness of these project partners with Cyprus is also one of the reasons why we have chosen to experiment with the targeted intervention set out above. More specifically, the deep familiarity of these project partners with the Cyprus context allows for an understanding of the political landscape around citizens' participation in Cyprus, including the role of CSOs and governmental actors that would be interested in both supporting the pilot assembly and taking forward the recommendations to the relevant powerholders. We have already reached out to relevant actors in Cyprus with whom we will work to advance our context-based analysis as explained above, using that to specify the design choices for the national pilot in the upcoming deliverables.

2.3. The Transnational Pilot: Enclave Deliberation Involving ‘the Deeply Affected’

Designing a transnational assembly with participants across multiple EU Member States is in and of itself a challenging task. Deliverable 3.3 shed light on the current European Citizens' Panels and how they already incorporate design features that aim to address some of the structural obstacles that prevent the participation of a diverse group of people in these Panels (e.g., by providing ad hoc support and compensation, a physically accessible venue and oversampling young participants). The Panels are an extremely well-resourced participatory activity, supported by significant budgetary and operational resources. An example is the fact that they provide

simultaneous translation to multiple languages to the participants in the room, reducing the barriers to communication between people speaking different languages.

However, Deliverable 3.3 also identified that, while there is a focus on young people and those from across socio-economic backgrounds, diversity is largely pursued through geographical terms, rather than also through forms of social marginalisation i.e., there are no specific recruitment measures for PMIMG or vulnerable communities. In addition, the Commission's description of 'hard-to-reach citizens' focuses on political disengagement, rather than on the structural or overlapping forms of marginalisation that might form barriers to participation. Equating 'hard-to-reach' with political disengagement is problematic from an intersectionality point of view. While those who rarely vote in European elections may indeed include those on the margins of EU societies, this framing individualises the problem and overlooks people whose participation is constrained by poverty, discrimination, language, insecure employment and housing status or disability, and who may be active in community or issue-based spaces yet remain invisible to recruitment strategies built around electoral disengagement. External assessments likewise call for broader representativity and note the top-down design and weak role for civil society in shaping inclusion criteria, reinforcing the need for complementary approaches that attend to overlapping forms of marginalisation (Gjaldbæk-Sverdrup E. et.al., 2023; Demidov et.al., 2023).

As such, our transnational pilot takes a complementary approach, aiming to address these gaps.¹³ Recognising that replicating the full-scale, multilingual infrastructure of the European Citizens' Panels would not be realistic within the confines of this research project, we instead aim to pilot and evaluate a transnational assembly model focusing on developing procedural and methodological innovations in the form of a targeted intervention that can address the areas for further development within European citizens' assemblies with regards to integrating and operationalising intersectionality.

Above, we explained the reasons why we chose to organise a transnational, EU-based pilot on the topic of housing. As we explain below, the choice of the topic for this pilot is related both to

¹³ We would like to thank the participants in the Essex Workshop on 'Designing Intersectional Citizens' Assemblies' which took place in July 2025, and particularly Dr Melisa Ross, for inspiring this idea. For a discussion on enclave deliberation as a form of empowering socially disadvantaged groups, see Ercan et al., 2025.

input phase choices (e.g., thinking about recruitment), but also to the *output* phase (e.g., thinking about the recipients of the assembly's recommendations). The European Commission is currently carrying out an Affordable Housing Dialogue, throughout 2025, with the aim of collecting knowledge and data from stakeholders across EU Member States (European Commission, 2025b). The Dialogue consists of three stages: a call for evidence that ran between 12 May and 4 June 2025, where 313 stakeholders and citizens contributed. According to the Commission, this stage will help outline the Commission's intended approach to the European Affordable Housing Plan. This was followed by a meeting of the Housing Advisory Board, which is a 15-member expert group tasked with providing concrete, independent policy recommendations for the Commission to consider in preparing the European Affordable Housing Plan. The third and final official stage of the Dialogue is a public consultation which has been running since 11 July and closed on 17 October, aimed at collecting views from the general public and experts on possible policy solutions. Based on the input from the Dialogue, the Commission will present its Affordable Housing Plan in 2026.

The transnational pilot will seek to **utilise** the contributions to the Dialogue, **add** to the Dialogue by bringing PMIMG voices into the conversation, and **contribute** to the eventual policy options that find their way in the EU Affordable Housing Plan. This approach is built on an understanding of the EU institutional structure and balance according to which a transnational assembly is one piece of a larger decision-making puzzle. As such, the specific aspect of the housing crisis that the transnational assembly will contribute to will be determined by examining, as part of the upcoming micro-design phase of the pilots, what the EU institutions have the competence to affect at the transnational level. This is in line with our context-based approach (Key Consideration 3), whereby the specificities of the level of governance in which an assembly takes part should be examined during the design of that assembly.

Linking the transnational assembly with existing priorities of the EU, on the one hand, and with the existing EU landscape of citizens' participation, on the other hand, will allow us to explore whether an enclave-style assembly, as described below, can meaningfully add to the participation of PMIMG voices in that landscape and, by extension, in the EU decision-making processes.

For the transnational pilot Citizens' Assembly design, we took inspiration from the **Subaltern Counterpublic** Model set out in Deliverable 2.3 (pp. 29-37). The model is itself inspired by Nancy

Fraser's (2014) concept of 'subaltern counterpublics' as discursive arenas where marginalised groups can deliberate free from pressures to conform to dominant narratives or majority opinions and then re-enter the main public sphere with strengthened viewpoints. The Subaltern Counterpublic Model in Deliverable 2.3 suggests ways in which counterpublics can be formed, managed, and organised *within* citizens' assemblies: based on identity or interest; and, taking place before, during, or after the main assembly. Inviting an already established counterpublic to participate in an assembly (e.g., at the information-providing throughput stage) was also seen as a potential avenue.

This model has potential to enhance the intersectional inclusion and deliberation qualities of an assembly by incorporating a safe deliberative space and amplifying minority voices by encouraging the sharing of stories, experiences, and perspectives unique to PMIMG. The idea relates to that of 'enclave deliberations', which refers to deliberation in a group of members **connected through some facet of their experiences or identity**. In the literature, enclave deliberations have been recommended as a way of including people who are traditionally marginalised or overlooked in sortition-based processes, the European Citizens Panels being one such process. By providing 'a safe, supportive space, enclave deliberations can facilitate excluded groups in clarifying their common aims, strengthening their arguments and developing recommendations' (Harris, 2021 p. 686; Wojciechowska, 2019). Enclaves, if connected to wider spheres of deliberation that foreground more traditional models of representation (such as sortition, or other broader consultation processes), can then be conceptualised as counterpublics which improve the intersectional character of the process.

We frame our transnational assembly as an enclave deliberation of this kind: a space oriented around those affected by an aspect of the housing crisis, who deliberate collectively, and whose recommendations are targeted towards the wider EU participatory democratic system. Our approach takes inspiration from **the 'most-deeply affected' principle** (Afsahi, 2020) as an alternative way of looking at the issue of representativeness in citizens' assemblies. This view aligns with the logic of enclaves which bring together excluded groups, which, in the context of the housing crisis in Europe, include vulnerable communities who face the greatest barriers to stable housing yet remain the least visible and least represented in policy processes. For example, Eurofound (2023) and the European Parliament (2020) note that groups such as people experiencing or at risk of homelessness, low-income renters, migrants, and single-parent households fall outside the narrow eligibility frameworks or outreach capacities of current

affordable housing programmes, while the Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA) (2025) highlights that their distinct experiences are seldom reflected in policymaking.

Therefore, instead of attempting to satisfy EU demographic representation within a relatively small group of 100 people, we instead adopt a view of intersectional inclusion inspired by the principle that ‘those most-deeply affected by both the current decision in question and the historical process and practices shaping the choices available’ should have a stronger claim to legitimacy than everyone else (Afsahi, 2020 p. 6). Traditional sortition approaches rely on the assumption that they will be perceived as democratically legitimate based on their alignment of a few demographic variables with their distribution in the general population. While there appears to be some empirical support for this assumption (Sortition Foundation, 2025), research has also demonstrated that non-participants’ perception of legitimacy depends less on the demographic composition of the body and more on the participants being ordinary citizens and not politicians (Pow et al., 2020). For example, Jacobs & Kaufmann (2019) found in a survey experiment that perceptions of democratic legitimacy were similar for citizens’ assembly-like deliberative exercises that used sortition and those using self-selection. Moreover, there is evidence that the ‘deeply affected’ principle may also have perceived democratic legitimacy with a wider public. For example, a probability-based sample of the Irish public investigating public attitudes towards science policy found that there was 63% agreement with statement, ‘People who will be directly affected by scientific research should have a say in how it develops’ (i.e., deeply affected principle) while the statement, ‘The general public should have a say in how science develops’ (i.e., disinterested public) only gained 43% agreement. This suggests that there may be democratic legitimacy in prioritising the views of those who are deeply affected by an issue. However, if ‘deeply affected’ shades into being perceived as special interests behaving selfishly there is a downside risk of perceived democratic legitimacy being lowered (Rasmussen & Reher, 2023).

We can also see some support for the idea of enclave-style deliberation in the strategy of the EU itself around public participation. The Commission’s Communication following up on the Conference on the Future of Europe sets out the possibility to convene Citizens’ Panels composed exclusively of young people whose deliberations would serve as a ‘youth test’ (Commission, 2022). As part of Deliverable 3.3, we looked at the first EU Young Citizens Assembly on Pollinators, which is ongoing. According to the European Commission, the Assembly will be exclusively composed of young people because ‘young people certainly have a particular stake at this debate, as they will live most of their lives with the consequences of the

[environmental] crisis and the decisions we take today’ (European Commission, 2025a). Although the wording does not refer directly to those ‘deeply affected’, it does allude to the need to give a special place in the process to a part of the broader population, in this case to the youth. It can thus be argued that the concept relating to those deeply affected is not entirely foreign to the EU’s current strategy.

The transnational pilot, therefore, seeks to explore ‘the deeply affected’ principle alongside the rationale behind the subaltern counterpublics model in the operationalisation of intersectionality to be tested in the transnational pilot citizens’ assembly. By bringing these voices together in a dedicated deliberative space, the transnational pilot seeks **to surface perspectives that are systematically absent from EU housing debates** and to test procedural innovations that could make such inclusion structurally sustainable. This design could yield practical insights to inform the potential use of transnational enclave deliberations as part of the European Citizens’ Panels.

An Overview of the Pilots’ Design			
Level	Local pilot	National pilot	Transnational pilot
Targeted Intervention	Community co-design	Intersectionality-driven recruitment and/or content	Enclave deliberation inspired by the deeply affected principle
Cross-cutting intervention	Facilitation		
Intersectionality guiding design choices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intersectionality as an analytical framework based on power relations understood in the relevant context • Awareness of our own positionality 		

Figure 7. An overview of the pilots’ design

V. Cross-Cutting Intervention: Embedding Intersectionality in Facilitation

The previous discussion explained the targeted interventions that this project aims to test in each of the three pilots planned to take place under Work Package 4. By way of contrast, the fourth intervention takes place across all three pilots and concerns the way in which the pilots will be facilitated and, connected to that, the way in which the facilitators will be trained. This section explains why we consider facilitation a good entry-point for embedding intersectionality considerations in citizens' assemblies, and in what ways we plan to operationalise intersectionality via the facilitation aspect of the three pilot assemblies. Similarly to the discussion above, the section complements and builds on the theoretical foundations of Work Package 2 and foregrounds the implementation phase of Work Package 4 and the subsequent policy recommendations of Work Package 5.

1. Advancing an Intersectionality-Informed Approach to Citizens' Assembly Facilitation

This section explains why we have chosen to explore facilitation across all three pilots as an area of intervention that is particularly amenable to intersectional considerations within the scope and the inevitable limitations of our project. It sets out our vision for an intersectionality-informed approach to facilitation. This vision is expressed through what we call '**activators of intersectionality**', which will apply to all three pilots and will assist in further designing the facilitation activities per pilot, implementing and evaluating those activities, and eventually drawing broader policy recommendations about the way in which intersectionality can be operationalised through facilitation in a citizens' assembly. These activators are set out here. Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2 will explain how the activators have been tailored to each pilot and the specific actions and activities that will be applied to each pilot separately. This ensures that intersectionality-informed facilitation as a cross-cutting intervention is inspired by the key consideration, explained under 'Methodology', whereby we should remain particularly attentive to the context of each individual pilot.

This section focuses on the role of facilitation in designing and conducting citizens' assemblies informed by an intersectional perspective. Like the rest of this deliverable, the discussion builds upon and complements the theoretical foundations of Work Package 2 (particularly Deliverables

2.2 and 2.3) and serves as a bridge between these earlier work packages, and the implementation phase of Work Package 4 followed by the policy-oriented reflections of Work Package 5. It starts by summarising briefly the role of facilitation and facilitators in citizens' assemblies and positing it within the framework and focus of the EU-CIEMBLY project. It then analyses how intersectionality theory is connected to facilitation and presents a set of operational tools and methods (called 'activators') that can lead to a more intersectionality-informed facilitation in current practices. As mentioned above, the more precise way in which these activators will be used in each of the pilots will be further set out in the forthcoming Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2 and will become part of the training of the facilitators that is planned to take place under Task 4.2 of the project.

1.1. The Case for Embedding Intersectionality in Facilitation

Why have we identified the stage of facilitation as a feature of citizens' assemblies that is particularly amenable to intersectional considerations? The starting point in our thinking process was that facilitation lies at the core of deliberative democratic processes such as citizens' assemblies. Facilitation is important in turning an assembly from a meeting of diverse people into a space where these diverse individuals can listen, learn, and reason together. Facilitation has been characterised as the craft of enabling collective work through conversations that are inclusive, meaningful, and productive (Escobar, 2011; 2019). In the EU-CIEMBLY's conceptual framework, therefore, facilitation plays a role in turning the three analytical qualities of inclusion, equality, and good deliberation, into practical applications in the interactions among participants.

In this sense, we see facilitation as both an avenue for implementing intersectionality considerations in the assembly process, and an operational tool for achieving intersectional deliberation.

In the absence of consideration of intersectionality, there is a risk that facilitation practices might overlook how power asymmetries and social hierarchies shape communication, despite techniques that have been developed so far to foster inclusive deliberation. Our contention is that intersectionality can provide an analytical lens through which facilitation can mitigate such inequalities.

In the EU-CIEMBLY framework, the facilitator is conceived not as a neutral moderator but an agent of democratic equity: a **reflective practitioner** who is aware of their own positionality and capable of navigating the complexities of group dynamics. As Deliverable 2.3 emphasises, inclusion and equality cannot be ‘controlled’ solely through design choices; they emerge through human interaction.¹⁴ Facilitation is seen as one of the primary interfaces between theory and practice, allowing intersectionality to be translated into lived deliberative experience.

The project’s approach to facilitation, therefore, embodies a central hypothesis: that inclusive **democratic innovation requires both structural design and relational practice**. In Deliverable 2.3, we had discussed relationality and interdependence as aspects that should guide a relational approach to the design choices for an intersectionality-oriented assembly. More specifically, ‘Model 6: Relationality and Interdependence’ from Deliverable 2.3 (pp. 54-60) explored ideas that could be operationalised in almost any assembly context, regardless of the rest of its design features. As stated in that deliverable, ‘it is almost a given that an assembly that aims to bring to the fore intersectionality considerations should incorporate some version of [the design features included in Model 6] in some way or another’. The Model prioritised placing emphasis on the values, goals, and commonalities that participants share, by allowing participants the time and space to get to know each other and laying the groundwork for deliberation from a place of respect.

In terms of connecting such ideas around relational practice with facilitation, we can be guided by the notion of facilitation as both a *technology of power*—structuring participation—and a *technology of care*—fostering respect, empathy, and mutual recognition among citizens deliberating together (Escobar, 2019). Escobar (2019), invites us to consider facilitation as a technology of power. Facilitators, as ‘experts of community’, operate through practices that shape and regulate specific forms of sociality, defining implicitly what it means to ‘communicate well’ or ‘to be a good deliberative citizen’. In this sense, facilitation is never fully neutral: it is an act of governing social relations that can both empower and normalise.

On the other hand, within the intersectional paradigm proposed by EU-CIEMBLY, facilitation is conceived as an act of democratic care that resists the reproduction of structural inequalities. The facilitator becomes an agent of equity, capable of reading and responding to power dynamics

¹⁴ Deliverable 2.3, pp. 10-11.

emerging among participants. The 'frontstage' and 'backstage' actions of a facilitator (Escobar, 2015), which span from the stage of orchestrating space and time to that of recording recommendations, are directed toward making marginalised voices visible and translating deliberation into politically relevant forms of knowledge. Seen in this light, facilitation is a **reflective and situated practice**: a craft (Escobar, 2019) learned through doing, imitation, and adaptation, yet grounded in a theoretical awareness of the dynamics of oppression and privilege that permeate every deliberative space.

Practically speaking, facilitation refers to the set of **practices, skills, and tools** that make it possible to enable public conversation in inclusive, meaningful, and productive ways (Escobar, 2011, 2019). In particular, within citizens' assemblies, facilitation is a crucial element to ensure that interactions among participants are truly deliberative and do not reproduce the inequalities and hierarchies of power present in society (Young, 2000; Landwehr, 2014). In the literature, many concepts and their implicit functions have been designed to describe the role of a facilitator in a citizens' assembly. Generally, a facilitator acts as an intermediary among various actors in the process: organisers, experts, and citizens. However, the facilitators themselves can assume different roles or be expected to embody at the same time multiple roles, for example having some knowledge of the topic addressed. The facilitator's role goes beyond time management or enforcing rules; it consists of building and maintaining the communicative conditions that allow everyone to contribute. This means fostering equal speaking opportunities, supporting mutual understanding, mediating conflicts, and promoting active listening that values different forms of expression—verbal, emotional, or narrative (Escobar et al., 2014; Dillard, 2013).

The facilitator holds 'a new political status' as a mediator between institutions and citizens, between technical and experiential knowledge (Rose, 1999; Escobar, 2019). In citizens' assemblies, this translates into a delicate balance between neutrality regarding the topic under discussion and non-neutrality toward the deliberative process itself. For the facilitator, holding this status (Landwehr, 2014) entails a dual commitment. The first commitment is to ensure that internal exclusion does not result from discussions that are dominated by voices that are more powerful than others or by those speaking in a more articulate language than others. Such forms of internal exclusion are widely documented in the deliberative democracy literature explored in Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2. The second commitment is to create conditions in which marginalised experiences and wealth of knowledge can be recognised and valued. **Therefore, the facilitator's role is not confined to procedural management but extends to an act of democratic care,**

aimed at balancing communicative power among participants. This act is translated in practice through strategies such as paraphrasing, summarising, reframing conflicts, promoting accessible language, and using humour as social lubricant (Hewer et al., 2019). This balancing does not translate to a numerical understanding of equality as equality of speaking time but rather relies on a substantive equality assessment of opportunities for expression, which may involve moderating the contributions of more privileged groups and expanding space for those with less voice (Escobar, 2019).

Against the above background, it is our project's contention that the role of the facilitators of an assembly can be improved *from an intersectionality point of view* when it is grounded on fostering communication and dialogue that are based on social justice (Habermas, 1984): ensuring that discursive power is genuine, redistributed to reflect the plurality of experiences and forms of knowledge present in society, based on mutual understanding. **Intersectionality-informed facilitation implies recognising the specific lived experiences of marginalisation and inequity of different social groups and adopting measures that allow these experiences to emerge and to be treated with respect and attention.** An intersectional approach to deliberation further recognises that inclusion cannot be reduced to the numerical presence of diverse participants. Instead, it depends on the quality of interaction and on whether the deliberative environment allows the participants to express their lived experiences and forms of knowledge without fear of dismissal or domination. In this sense, facilitation becomes an avenue through which intersectionality takes form.

1.2. Embedding Intersectionality in Facilitation through the EU-CIEMBLY Pilot Assemblies

The above discussion has explained the reasons why experimenting with embedding intersectionality-informed facilitation can further the EU-CIEMBLY project's ambition to contribute to the design of citizens' assemblies as spaces capable of addressing patterns of exclusion and marginalisation that persist within participatory and deliberative innovations. The following discussion answers the question: In what way are we planning to embed intersectionality considerations in the three pilot assemblies? This refers to the project's overall vision of *facilitation*

*activators*¹⁵ that apply to all three pilots, with further details about specific *facilitation activities* per pilot to come in Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2.

Figure 8: The cross-cutting intervention of facilitation across deliverables

1.2.1. Activators of intersectionality across all three pilots

Translating the principles of intersectional inclusion and equality into practice via facilitation requires concrete and adaptable facilitation methods. Facilitation within citizens' assemblies is an already well-established topic of research, and the academic literature (including practical guides) on it is vast (e.g., Curato et al., 2021; Escobar, 2019; Goodin, 2000; Morán et al., 2025; O'Doherty et al., 2012; von Schneidemesser et al., 2023). Our project team recognises the already existing lessons drawn from the experience with citizens' assemblies' implementation and evaluation on the ground, and we have benefitted greatly from the contribution of persons who have been engaged in these aspects both to our Workshop on 'Designing Intersectional Citizens' Assemblies' that took place in July 2025, and to the interviews that we conducted as part of Work

¹⁵ The UN Intersectionality Resource Guide and Toolkit similarly identifies 'Intersectionality Enablers' albeit in the context of Development Programmes.

Package 3.¹⁶ Following the rationale of the current Deliverable 3.4, and specifically the above discussion on the objectives of the pilots, our purpose here is to **build on** existing experiences and modes of facilitation to explore how intersectionality can be embedded within citizens' assemblies via facilitation. In this section, potential 'intersectionality activators' are identified that could foster intersectional deliberation across all three pilots. These activators are transversal and apply regardless of whether the process is conducted at the local, national, or transnational level. More specific guidelines will be adopted under Deliverable 4.2 and adapted to the specific design and context of each pilot.

Following the project's Key Consideration 4 of 'Adopting Targeted Interventions' in the design of the pilots for the project, the following section details three activators which have been designed to be integrated within all three of our pilots and to be tested in practice in order to then inform existing citizens' assembly practices. In other words, the intersectionality activators underpin the cross-cutting intervention of intersectionality-informed facilitation in the context of the EU-CIEMBLY pilots. They will be used to inform and influence the design of specific facilitation actions in each of the pilots, taking into account the location and context of each of those pilots—thus aligning with our Key Consideration 3 of adopting a 'context-based approach'. Furthermore, they have been designed in line with our normative understanding of intersectionality (Key Consideration 1) that pays attention both to individual and structural dimensions of intersectional marginalisation, in that individual identities and perceptions are shaped by the synthesis of inequality structures. As will be seen, 'being mindful of our own positionality' (Key Consideration 2) is an integral part of our proposed intersectionality-informed facilitation method.

¹⁶ See, respectively, Deliverable 3.2 and Deliverables 3.1 and 3.3.

Figure 9: Activators of intersectionality-informed facilitation

Activator 1: Value diverse communication modes

Facilitation models grounded in liberal conceptions of deliberation that privilege rational argument and neutrality risk silencing those who communicate differently or who are positioned at the margins of dominant social structures (Young, 2001; Karpowitz et al., 2009). Intersectionality-driven facilitation values multiple communicative modes, such as storytelling, emotional expression, humour, and embodied knowledge, as legitimate contributions to collective reasoning. This activator will be operationalised in Deliverable 4.2 by training facilitators in specific, observable techniques, examples of which might include: (a) explicitly inviting storytelling and personal testimony as valid forms of evidence, not just 'anecdote'; (b) using visual or arts-based methods (e.g., collective mind-mapping) to capture non-verbal contributions; and (c) implementing a 'listen-reflect-speak' rule, allowing for structured silent reflection before deliberation to aid participants who are less comfortable with rapid, adversarial debate.

For the EU-CIEMBLY pilots, this approach means that facilitators must work to ensure that what counts as 'reasoned discourse', i.e., following a rational and (traditional) deliberative debate approach, is accompanied by a **relational dimension that reflects the diversity of experiences in the room**. By so doing, facilitation becomes a practice of epistemic justice, countering the dominance of elite or expert language and creating conditions for the emergence of alternative

knowledge that informs more equitable collective outcomes, through fostering open dialogue that may also imply divergence of perspectives, the sharing of personal experience, stories, and testimonies.

Activator 2: Understand how power operates in deliberative settings

In attempting to counter elite dominance, the concept of the *matrix of domination* developed by Patricia Hill Collins (2019) provides a useful lens for understanding how power operates in deliberative settings. According to Collins, interlocking systems of oppression—such as heteropatriarchy, capitalism, colonialism, and imperialism—structure both individual identities and institutional practices. In the context of citizens' assemblies, these dynamics manifest in subtle ways: who speaks first, who is interrupted, whose emotions are validated, and whose arguments are perceived as credible. Facilitators, as key intermediaries, are positioned within this matrix. Their task is to **identify and mitigate these power dynamics**, transforming the deliberative space into one where participants can safely engage across their differences. This requires both procedural fairness and contextual sensitivity.

Intersectionality-oriented facilitation ensures that deliberation becomes an inclusive process of collective reasoning, rather than a contest of communicative privilege. This understanding will be translated into concrete actions in Deliverable 4.2, examples of which might include: (a) proactively using a 'round robin' (go-around) speaking order to prevent dominant voices from monopolising the floor; (b) actively 'stacking' the speaking queue to prioritise participants from marginalised groups who have not yet spoken; and (c) gently intervening to 'name' and re-frame non-deliberative power dynamics (e.g., 'I notice we've interrupted [Participant X] twice now, I'd like to hear them finish their thought').

An intersectionality-informed approach to facilitation demands that facilitators identify the social, cultural, and political context of the assembly – whether local, national, or transnational, and adapt their methods accordingly. Central to this approach is an awareness of **relational power**, including **the facilitator's own positional privilege and power**, and an understanding that individuals may occupy positions of relative privilege in one context while experiencing marginalisation in another (UN Women, 2021 p. 14). Based on this awareness, facilitators should be ready to provide differentiated and adapted forms of support: more time, translation, small-group reflection, or facilitation styles that are adapted to allow engagement of participants on an

equal footing. This principle echoes EU-CIEMBLY's broader understanding of intersectional inclusion that favours affirmative practices which compensate for structural marginalisation.

For facilitators, this implies a reconfiguration of their role: they are not mere neutral arbiters ensuring procedural symmetry, but agents of substantive equality and inclusion who play an active role in balancing power dynamics. This may involve moderating dominant voices, encouraging less confident participants, or adjusting group composition to avoid isolation of minority members. In this way, intersectional equality-oriented facilitation ensures that deliberation becomes an inclusive process of collective reasoning, rather than a contest of communicative privilege.

Activator 3: Practise reflexivity

Facilitation has become increasingly professionalised in deliberative and participatory contexts (Lee, 2015; Bherer et al., 2017). Within the EU-CIEMBLY project, however, facilitators are not external or neutral agents detached from the research process. Rather, they are integral members of the consortium and **active participants in the experimental design** of intersectionality-oriented citizens' assemblies. This deliberate choice reflects, and can be justified by, both practical and epistemological considerations. Practically, the three EU-CIEMBLY pilots aim to test innovative, context-sensitive facilitation models that require close coordination between researchers, community representatives, and institutional partners. The facilitators' familiarity with the theoretical foundations of the project, particularly the analytical principles of intersectional inclusion, equality, and good deliberation outlined in Deliverable 2.2, ensures that their practice remains aligned with the project's overarching objectives.

In addition, the researchers involved in the EU-CIEMBLY project have strong experience in qualitative research and the conducting of focus groups, workshops, and other deliberative fora. They also come from different parts of Europe and can speak different languages, which should ensure their ability to facilitate across diverse cultural and linguistic environments. While an initial training and precise instructions will be provided to the facilitators under Task 4.2, there must be a balance between a structured process and sensitivity to local dynamics, ensuring that deliberation remains meaningful in each setting. Training, therefore, should focus both on technical skills—such as time management or moderation—and on reflexive capacities, empathy, and situational awareness.

Reflexivity is a particularly crucial aspect of the facilitators' role in EU-CIEMBLY. It requires that practitioners reflect on how their own background and identities shape the process; challenge and uncover their own unconscious biases and proactively seek feedback from those experiencing intersectional discrimination; remain conscious of how their position and status may inhibit others from speaking up; and, reflect at various points how their own background identities shape the process (UN Women, 2022). Beyond the facilitators per se, and related to their work, we contend that reflexivity is something that participants should also practise throughout the assembly if they are to become more aware of their positionality and the power dynamics within the group.

In addition to embedding mechanisms for **positionality review** in the pilots' design process (see Key Consideration 2 above), a reflexive approach can be embedded in the pilot process e.g., through two formal mechanisms: (a) mandatory daily debrief sessions between all facilitators and a 'lead facilitator' to discuss power dynamics, challenges, and individual biases that emerged during the day; and (b) a structured 'reflexivity journal' to be used by facilitators throughout the process (prompted by questions from the facilitator training delivered as part of Deliverable 4.2) and reviewed during the debriefs. The forthcoming Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2 will further explore how such reflective practices will be formally integrated into the pilots' micro-design.

1.3. Concluding Remarks on Facilitation as a Cross-Cutting Intervention

As we mentioned above, one of the key considerations in our attempt to operationalise intersectionality is engaging in a context-based analysis. For facilitators of citizens' assemblies, this means being mindful of the time and place of the assembly, including whether it takes place online or face-to-face. For the purposes of the EU-CIEMBLY pilot assemblies, facilitation practices need to be adapted to fit the local-national-transnational context, and to fit the underlying theoretical model and purpose of each pilot. Different types of intersectionality-informed activities may need to take place in the different pilots.

For instance, for the local pilot, which is based on the Power Sharing model, facilitation methods should be informed by the co-design and shared governance model of the pilot. Community advisors and representatives of marginalised groups should be involved from the preparatory phase, participating in defining agendas and rules. Facilitators will act here as bridges between

institutional organisers and community actors, ensuring that deliberation reflects the priorities of those affected by the issue in question. In the national pilot, which seeks to explore Descriptive and Discursive Representation, facilitators will have to manage a process that takes place for the first time in Cyprus. Most likely, participants will not have experience with these types of participatory exercises and thus facilitators should balance structured deliberation with flexibility to accommodate narrative and experiential contributions, while remaining alert to risks of representational burden. Finally, in the transnational pilot inspired by the Subaltern Counterpublics Model, facilitators should be acting as custodians of this safe(r) space by ensuring that the insights produced by the group are accurately transposed into recommendations that can then be brought into, and inform, other consultation processes. Across all levels, facilitation practices must therefore be context-dependent but theoretically coherent, reflecting the intersectional and systematic logic of the EU-CIEMBLY project.

Overall, the EU-CIEMBLY project envisions facilitators not merely as managers of discussion but as agents of intersectional change. As Wojciechowska (2019) argues, democratic innovation requires practitioners who can directly engage disempowered groups and invite them into leadership positions. Within this logic, facilitators are part of the project's broader commitment to redistributing power within democratic processes. By modelling inclusive communication, mediating across social divides, and elevating marginalised voices, facilitators demonstrate the practical meaning of intersectionality in action. Their work contributes not only to the quality of deliberation but also to participants' experience of recognition, empowerment, and collective agency.

In this sense, facilitation embodies the bridge between the project's theoretical ambitions and its democratic ethos. They enact, in the microcosm of the assembly, the principles that EU-CIEMBLY seeks to advance: that equality cannot be achieved without equity, that inclusion requires active care, and that deliberation is not only a cognitive but also an ethical and relational process.

VI. Conclusion

Deliverable 3.4 marks the project's transition from evaluating existing citizens' assembly practices to designing three pilots that aim to test how intersectionality can be operationalised in reality. Building on the project's analytical and normative lens, which is comprised of the qualities of intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation, and our categorising dimensions of input, throughput, and output choices, the pilots aim to translate theory into practice by selecting concrete design features to examine across local, national, and transnational levels.

This report set out the overarching vision and parameters for each pilot, as well as the key considerations that have guided our decisions, while intentionally preserving flexibility to adapt to context- and power- dynamics as the project proceeds. We have explained that, across the three pilots, we aim to test targeted intersectional interventions that draw from the project's operationalisation models as these were set out in Deliverable 2.3, thus ensuring continuity between our theoretical and practical work. The purpose of this approach is to generate evidence about which design choices (and which combination of design choices) have the capacity to enhance intersectional equality, inclusion, and good deliberation, in the practice of citizens' assemblies. In parallel, we will adopt a cross-cutting intervention that seeks to embed intersectionality into facilitation. Here, facilitators hold an important role in mediating power imbalances and ensuring that less-heard perspectives shape the deliberation and outcomes of the assembly.

By implementing the above interventions, the next steps of the project aim to illustrate ways in which the EU-CIEMBLY framework's values are operationalised for the benefit of the participants and for the benefit of the current community of practice. This goal will be materialised not least through the evaluation stage of the project, which will examine the key hypotheses raised in the work completed so far. This will include issues such as how different recruitment configurations affect experiences of inclusion; whether intersectionality-informed facilitation mitigates internal exclusion; and, whether participants' experiences of a citizens' assembly is affected by the inclusion of intersectional dimensions in the topic and expertise presented to participants.

In light of the above, Deliverable 3.4 not only draws on Work Package 2 conceptually but also feeds back into it in a structured manner: the four-dimensional framework of Deliverable 2.2 guides the design of the pilots, the models of Deliverable 2.3 shape the interventions that will be

tested, and the pilots themselves become empirical sites where the project can evaluate its theoretical assumptions.

The next steps of the project consist of Tasks 4.1 and 4.2, which will lead, respectively, to more detailed design and implementation plans for the pilots (Deliverable 4.1), and a tailored facilitation training programme (Deliverable 4.2).

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